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A Representation of Women Subjugation in K.R.Meera's Hang Woman

Meera A S¹, Dr R Jinu²

Abstract

K. R. Meera (born 19 February 1970) is an Indian author and journalist, who writes in Malayalam. She was born in Sasthamcotta, Kollam district in Kerala. She worked as a journalist in *Malayala Manorama* but later resigned to concentrate more on writing. She started writing fiction in 2001 and her first short-story collection *Ormayude Njarambu* was published in 2002. Her novel *Arachar* came out in 2012 and became quite a sensation in the Malayalam literary scene and it went on to win the Central Sahitya Akademi award. In 2015, Penguin brought out the English translation of this novel, titled, *Hangwoman*. Although, *Hangwoman* is a Malayalam novel, the themes that it deals with are pan-Indian. It depicts the multi-layered othering in Indian society and it also reflects the predicaments of contemporary India. The novel stands out for its close portrayal of the life of a marginalised woman and her resistance to the subjugation that is meted out to her. She received several awards including the Kerala Sahitya Akademy Award, Odakkuzhal Award, Vayalar Award and Kendra Sahitya Akademy Award for her novel *Aarachaar*.

Re-reading of Hang Woman

Most societies are male-dominated where a woman is only supposed to be a mother, an ideal wife and a homemaker with multifarious roles attributed to her in the family. As a wife and mother, her service of sacrifice, tolerance and submissiveness are her required attributes. Furthermore, her admired qualities of

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adjustment make her life faithful and obedient. But this individual self of a woman has very little recognition in the patriarchal society and it leads to her self-eacement. Mary Ann Fergusson opines that: “In every age, women have been seen primarily as mother, wife, mistress, and as a sex object—their roles in relationship to men!” (Fergusson 4-5)

K. R. Meera, an extraordinary writer, brilliantly expresses feminist sensibility and philosophy and vividly depicts the galaxy of women, their passion, pain, battle for survival, and inner conflict. She depicts women’s suffering and how men and patriarchal society are responsible for women’s predicament and existence. The women in her stories are generally unafraid and strong, refusing to conform to society’s expectations. The protagonists of Meera’s stories would remain consistent in their character attributes while demonstrating their existence regardless of the consequences that they would face in their lives.

Everyone Loves a Good Hanging is a prodigiously long, intricate, and compelling story that explores themes of violence, grief, death, love, sexual abuse, trauma, the psyche of the executioner and the executed, and the exploitation of women trapped in the mud of existence for generations. It was initially written in Malayalam by K.R. Meera, and J Devika translated it beautifully and skilfully. The book version of *Aarachaar*, also known as the “Executioner” or “Hangwoman,” was released by DC Books in 2012 after it had previously been serialised in *Madhyamam Weekly* for 53 straight volumes. The *Hangwoman* title appeared in the English translation of *Aarachaar*.

Hangwoman, a first-person tale, explores the protagonist Chetna Grddha Mullick’s anxiety, inner conflict, and transformation into a hang-woman. The story shows her transformation from a submissive, obedient child to a fierce, stubborn woman who has been through many trials. Chetna, a 22-year-old lady of strength and tenacity, fights to carry on her family’s tradition of becoming an executioner. She became India’s first executioner who was a woman. She hangs not just the criminal, but also the arrogance of men in general. Chetna did not have an easy road to becoming a hangwoman but it was a route paved with thorns that caused her to suffer as Shelley did:

“I bleed when I fall upon the thorns of existence.” Chetna recounts the suffering and adversity of women about whom her grandmother regales her, along with her own struggles. Chetna became aware of how women have been constrained by the shackles of tradition and male chauvinism throughout history as a result of the women’s tales. The oppression and dominance seemed as though they were stifling the fundamental spirit of women. The women put a lot of effort to break these bonds but to no effect.

The epic book *Hangwoman* is a huge, powerful coiled rope. It is set in Chitpur, Kolkata, and rubs up against Nimtala’s smouldering ghat beside the Ganga. Everywhere you turn, death is evident in its sights, noises, and odour. In this urban underworld, death is the only source of daily sustenance. A family of hereditary hangmen who now offer tea to the grieving only sees brisk business when the streets are filled with hearses and bodies are burning brightly on pyres.

The Grddha Mullick family has a long history that dates back to 400 B.C. However, because there have been fewer executions in recent years, they are now living in poverty. The main character of the book Chetna was a smart student who excelled in her plus two. She must, however, discontinue her studies after plus two owing to budgetary limitations. Her father, Phanibhushan Grddha Mullick, a hangman who is now 88 years old, claims to have carried out 451 hangings. Her grandmother (Thakuma), father’s brother (whom she calls Kaku) and his wife, as well as her disabled brother (Ramu da) and his wife, who had their limbs amputated by the father of a criminal who was put to death by Phanibhushan, round out her family (Kakima). Sukhdev, her uncle, also known as Kaku, is an elderly guy who is close to 65 years old. Rari and Champa, his two little kids, are five and 10 years old, respectively.

Due to his position, Phanibhushan continues to come under intense media scrutiny; yet, he is adamant that Chetna’s picture never be made public. The reason for this is that he wants to spare her from the same heinous catastrophe that claimed the life of his son, Ramu da, Chetna’s older brother. Amartya Ghosh, the industrialist from Kolkata who had killed Chandresen Ghosh and his three children, had been hanged with Phanibhushan acting as his hangman. In an effort to save his son’s death, Amartya Ghosh’s father begged

Phanibhushan to intervene. Phani, however, is convinced that he must follow his job regardless of what his morals are and will not budge. Following Ramu da, Phani's son, returns from college two days after Amartya was executed, his father Ramu da, Phani's son, gets hacked in the limbs by his father after he returns from college two days after Amartya was put to death. The sole kid of Phani is now crippled and depressed as a result. Since there won't be anybody else to care for the family once he retires, Phani is anxious that his daughter Chetna obtain employment with the government. Chetna starts working as a hangwoman as her father's helper. However, she had to continue the family tradition alone while her father, Phani, was in prison for the murder of his brother and sister-in-law. Phani takes tremendous pleasure in his career and the lengthy history of his family's involvement in this field.

Kumar Sanjeev Mitra works as a reporter for CNC and a TV journalist. He wished to report on the execution of Jatindranath. This is the reason he travels to Phanibhushan. Chetna was on her way to the market when he covertly shot her. Chetna entered the spotlight quickly. Mitra supports Phanibhushan in his efforts to persuade government representatives to make Chetna the first woman in the nation to be hanged. For Chetna, he serialised the television show *Hang Woman's Diary*. She attends the studio with him and engages with the audience. Under the glaring lights of television cameras, her life starts to take off from this point. Chetna, the first female executioner in history, is all of a sudden pitchforked into public stardom. TV cameras and mikes stretched towards her to take her interview. Initially, she fears facing the camera but later shows her confidence:

“I faced them like a terrorist hemmed in by gun-toting commandos. What's more, she goes on to bowl her newfound captive audience over with her astute, precise responses. Chetna is being questioned in *Hang-woman's Diary*: But what if he [father] withdraws? You are the assistant hangman. What would be your stand if you had to undertake the task by yourself, (193) ...I sighed deeply. Then as the symbol of Indian womanhood and self-respect, I proclaimed: surely”!(195)

The dynamics of death by hanging, which are marketed in daily exclusive prime-time slots, turn the father and daughter into

overnight superstars. She is no longer a typical lady. For the first time ever, a woman has been chosen to carry out an execution. Now, she represents power and self-respect to the entire globe because Sanjeev's programme has a female executioner, its TRP ratings have never been higher.

Sanjeev is a dishonest voluptuous man. His father was a Naxalite and his mother was a prostitute. He pretends to help Chetna in becoming an executioner and promises her father to marry her. He appears to be a good man and impresses everyone with his winsome personality and pleasing behaviour. He insults Chetna in his first meeting and terrifies her by saying "I wanted to fuck you". He misbehaves with her when she is alone. His words and behaviour terrify and shock a tender girl Chetna. He steals the golden coin of her grandmother, a legacy which she cherished with deep love. He steals a Saree and an ear stud from a shop. He is responsible for the quarrel that arose between Phani and Kaku that resulted in Ramu's death. He arranges a TV Show for Chetna a Hang-woman's Diary. Initially, Chetna is scared to face the camera but gradually gains confidence and captivates the audience with her resolute demeanour and engrossing tales. When she completes her first execution she is brought to the studio by Sanjeev secretly. He wanted to earn huge TRP for his channel and fame for himself by interviewing India's first woman executioner. She forces Chetna to show the public a demo of a mock execution. The trauma which Chetna undergoes he is unable to comprehend. He pays no attention to her agony and conflict rather he forces her to face the camera and narrate the incident. Addressing his viewers Sanjeev says: "Viewers may be eager to know how Chetna hanged Jatindrath Banerjee today. How it took place and where, and what she did. Here we will create the experience for you"

Chetna Mullick a symbol of strength and self-respect for all women in India and the whole world boldly hangs Sanjeev and bravely steps ahead. Her face glows with a strange sense of contentment. She says to herself, "What the world gave me, I returned to it". An idol of Durga was presented to her by Sanjeev's mother. This Durga idol is created by soil and that soil is collected from the area where the prostitutes live. The men to gratify their lust have created a world of

prostitutes. The men kneel and bend before Durga idol in a symbolic way bending before a prostitute: The statue of Durga is made of soil taken from the beshya's doorsteps that is because the ego of the man who crosses it unravels and falls on the ground there.

The novel presents a picture gallery of women from the past to the present. The abject condition of women, their trials, tribulation, ordeals, molestation, revenge, passion for men, to whom to love and other different facets of their life are brought forth very vividly and exquisitely. Chetna has grown up listening to the stories of various women, and the myth of femininity as a weaker gender. At many points of time, she compares her position and condition with them. Chetna's Thakuma and Ma narrate their plight and remind Chetna of her weakness as a woman. Showalter comments on the acceptance and internalization of man's tyranny as fate:

“We have seen our foremothers as mindless down-trodden souls, accepting century after century the fetters of their lot with passivity, unheeding or incapable of perceiving their exclusion from society”. (Showalter, 11)

Chetna needs to get settled in life so she should accept Sanjeev as her husband. Chetna's mother is very anxious about her future. She requests her to accept Sanjeev's proposal and do all that can please him hence entrapping him into marriage. She asks her to appease and adore Sanjeev because men are like gods and need to be pleased by women. She says,

“You have a big future, Chetu. Don't ruin it. She sat up and looked into my eyes. For women like us, marriage is an escape route. It was for me. A place to sleep... some food, at least once a day...Listen to me, men are like gods. If they have no one to fall at their feet or beg or worship them three times a day, they are mere stones”(251)

Women have been suppressed and exploited for centuries and have become the prey of men's lust. It is a world where men dominate and women have to undergo it grudgingly. The old women or less attractive suffer the negligence of her husband and the beautiful women are being seduced ruthlessly by men. Phani says proudly to Sanjeev that he had relationships with four women in his life and that he lost interest in his old wife. In his opinion, men do not grow old - neither their body nor their passion for women. A woman generally loses her charm and attraction at the age of thirty to thirty-

five after giving birth to children and fails to hold the attention of her husband. He is a man physically active at the age of fifty. On being asked by Sanjeev what was the reaction of his wife to his liaison. He says that women in general are able to gauge or guess the liaison of their husbands. She knows about it. But she can't go against her master - her husband. The Indian patriarchal system accepts grudging acceptance and subordination on the part of women. Indian womanhood gets its proper place within 'wifeness' and 'motherhood'; as *Manusmṛiti* enunciates the ideals and norms for becoming an ideal wife. The primary ideology of Hindu patriarchy was denoted in *Manusmṛiti* as the wife is expected to be thrifty and do her work cheerfully, obey her husband in life and devoid of any qualities and observe celibacy till death. The story of Tripurasundari, her molestation by men and her revenge on them abounds with hair-raising descriptions. Her beauty and innocent laugh became a curse for her. Her grandmother reminds Chetna of the story of Tripurasundari whenever she laughs. According to Grandmother, the female should not laugh otherwise it will bring calamities:

“Women should not laugh. That's a bad omen. The house where a woman's laughter rings – it won't be long before it collapses. ... When Pingalakeshini laughed, not just the house, but the very land fell”. (172-73)

Chetna tells us the pathetic story of Utpalvarna, a woman who suffers from seduction, mistrust and desertion. She was pregnant when her husband set off to trade. His family cast doubts on her chastity and she has to leave home full-bellied. After giving birth to her child to a resting place she went in search of food for the child. She didn't find her child after returning. Stricken with grief she decided to go to her natal home. On the way, she is captured by Devadutta who was bewitched by her beauty. He forcibly made her his bride. She submitted to him but a man can't trust the loyalty of another man's wife. Devadutta is always suspicious about her loyalty and devotion so tortures her with unending bickering. One day, while fighting her he hit Utpalvarna and the baby whom she was feeding fell down. It was a big shock for her to lose her child the second time. Unable to bear the pain of separation from her child, Utpalvarna went to commit suicide. She was rescued by a young man. Seduced by her beauty, he made her his wife. The helpless,

hopeless and homeless, Utpalvarna has to surrender the passion of this young man. Beauty and lustre decay with the passage of time and hence the passion of man. The old and aged Utpalvarna was discarded like a peel. Her husband brought a young girl to satisfy his passion. Utpalvarna felt shattered and was ridden with jealousy. Utpalvarna dashed the young bride. She wanted to kill her who had snatched her position. She saw a large scar on the back of the head of the young girl (284). The girl narrated her tragic past and the conditions through which she is being separated from her mother. Her mother thought her dead when she accidentally fell down on the ground and committed suicide. Now Utpalvarna realized that this girl was her own daughter. Shocked by her own deed and tragic turn of her life Utpalvarna set off on a journey seeking the meaning of life, relationships and experience (284). She meets Buddha and one day gains enlightenment. She enjoys meditating. Once she went to a forest to meditate. A monk grabbing this opportunity unleashed his lust on her. The severe wounds on the body of Utpalvarna shocked even Buddha.

In a patriarchal society which is male-dominated, male-identified and male-centred, all decisions are carried out by men. Women are not given the right to choose a life partner. Adrienne Rich provides a comprehensive definition of the term patriarchy:

“A familial-social, ideological, political system in which men—by force, direct pressure, or through ritual, tradition, law, and language, customs, etiquette, education, and the division of labour, determine what part women shall or shall not play, and in which the female is everywhere subsumed under the male”.(57–58)

Niharika, Chetna's sister, was harmed by her father's authority and approval. When a young man arrived at Nimtala ghat to administer his father's last rites, Niharika fell in love with him. Under the protection of each other's love and loyalty, the couple had a happy existence. In opposition to this union, Phani violently shattered the Durga statue that Niharika's boyfriend had given her as a gift. Phani was furious with Niharika. Don't forget that this is a hand that has hung 455 people, he would constantly remind her. “Reduce the length of the rope a bit, and physicians won't be able to identify whether it was murder or suicide,” Phani (202) warned Niharika, claiming that he had the power to turn murder into suicide. (198)

Niharika was forcibly wed to a different guy. Her life was a living nightmare due to her husband and in-laws' torment. She returned to look for her sweetheart, her life force, unable to let go of her love and concerned by her husband's abuse. If his daughter continued to harbour feelings for another guy after being married, Phani believed it would be a grave disgrace to his family. Niharika took a risk and paid dearly for it. Phani executed her to death. This heinous murder of an innocent girl was converted into suicide. Threatening Chetna, Phani says

“Chetna, only my word carries weight in this house, Father said, trying very hard to control himself. I have made some demands of the government. If they don't agree, I have to take hard decision. And whatever they may be, you will have to obey”. (204)

The women have to suffer various kinds of oppression in a patriarchal society. Indu Prakash Singh writes:

“Whether it is child marriage, rape, dowry death, bride burning, child abuse, wife battering sexual assault or domestic violence, each form of oppression, pins down her sordid tale from womb to her tomb that map and draw the contours of her decadent, capitalist, casteist, criminal patriarchal society”. (Indian Women 24-25)

False promises are used to defraud the women. Chetna recounts the tale of the actress Binodini, who became a prostitute after being duped by her boyfriend. Everyone is captivated by Binodini's dazzling beauty and amazing acting. Both Girish Chandra Ghosh and Binodini desired to construct a large theatre. Ghosh came to understand that substantial finance is necessary for the realisation of his idea. So, in order to get money, he persuades Binodini to engage in prostitution. As she listened to his desire to use her as a prostitute for their fantasy, she was heartbroken.

“She was rendered speechless when he told her, you are after all a beshya, what do you have to lose? ...My life is full of bednagathas, heroic tales of sorrow, she wrote later in her autobiography”.(221)

Gosh seduces her by making fictitious promises to rename the theatre in her honour: He swears to rename the theatrical company after her once it's established. She had no other option than to become a prostitute in order to give birth to Sita, Draupadi, Radha, and Savitri on stage. When the building is finished, Ghosh breaks his pledge. He refers to it as the Star Theatre. Binodini is astonished to

learn that she quit acting when her career was at its peak.

The men were seduced by Binodini's superb acting and performance. The wealthy guys were willing to pay any price to acquire her and own her. A Marwari millionaire named Gurumukh Ray was seduced by her when she was singing lyrically and delivering her discourse with amazing dexterity. He was willing to pay any amount of money if Binodini could be made his concubine. (221) She begins to pay a visit to Gurumukh Ray's bedroom, a young Zamindar, in an effort to gather money to finish the Star Theatre. Gurumukh has a possessive attitude towards her and refuses to share her. She is asked to stop acting by him. However, he loses his rage when she acts against his wishes, grabs her by the hair, and bellows: "Betrayer! Whore"! Binodini looked at him with ease, as if she were on stage portraying Draupadi or Sita, and grinned. Then she delivered the most powerful line she had ever uttered in her life, "It is you men who have taught us to betray"! (224)

She gave up acting when she was 20 to become a wealthy man's concubine. This boyfriend has also abandoned her. She is left with little choice but to go back to her previous residence, a dilapidated home on the prostitute's street. She returns to her previous life as a prostitute because of the man's constant lies and abandonment. The situation of prostitutes is highlighted throughout the book. Many women are compelled to work in this industry in large cities owing to poverty or other factors. Chetna recounts the ladies lining up at the Sonagachi red light district.

"On both sides of the lanes too narrow for even a single vehicle to ply, there milled around women, fat and thin, fair and dark and wheatish, all made up with layers of rose powder and heavy kohl, clad in tight blouse that revealed their breasts and midriff, with or without a bindi on their foreheads. They stood there waiting, hands on hips, chest wide open".(224)

Chetna also felt the pain of prostitutes who are not brought by men:

"I walked past women with stony faces whom no one had yet bought. They waited with paint and sweat running down their face and neck, legs tiring, spirits flagging, and perhaps feeling the pangs of hunger".(226)

Men have long considered women as inferiors, Virginia Woolf

claims in *A Room of One's Own*. "In the society, males are the ones who define everything" (Woolf 1929: 28). Laws, customs, and taboos are either meant to oppress women or favour males. Women's feelings should not be considered while making decisions that were created by males. For murdering her husband as he was having sex with another woman, Kadmbhari received a death sentence. She had given him a severe head blow.

"There were two charges against her. First, she murdered her husband, her living god. Second, she had interrupted the sexual act, which made a man's life as a man, meaningful. The Pandits in royal court debated for a long while about which of these was the more sinful transgression". (211)

Mosh, the guy called to hang her, questioned her, "Why did you kill the man you loved so dearly?" She said that she wanted to die quickly so that she might see her spouse after death and that she wanted to release her husband from that evil lady. The work shows the persecution, abuse, and molestation of afflicted women in a patriarchal society, as well as their predicament and suffering.

Conclusion

K.R. Meera's dedication to women's problems has become stronger over time. She has a strong sense of compassion, and her stories portray oppression against organisations and mechanisms that legitimise familial control, official authority, and injustice wherever it exists. She had to identify the social outliers who resisted the patriarchy's ruthless exploitation. Through *Hang Woman*, she depicted the politics and history of India, with a woman as the central character. Moreover, Meera has hung violence, injustice and ego that prevailed in the country in her magnum opus. As K.R. Meera writes in her Acknowledgements page about women, "Those who did not seek them out would never know that they had indeed lived". It is found that once these women understand who they are and what they are capable of, they rise out of their own ashes and become epitomes of power and strength. Through *Chetana*, Meera is set to hang the male chauvinism in Indian society and portrays *Chetana* as an absolute power in a male-dominated society.

Bibliography

Butler, Judith. *Gender Trouble: Feminism and the subversion of Identity*. New York: Routledge, 1999.

- Beauvoir, De Simone. *The second Sex*. Trans. H.M. Parshley. Harmondsworth: Penguin, 1983.
- Fergusson, Mary Ann. *Images of Women in Literature*. Houghton Mifflin Co Boston, 1973. Print.
- Iyer N. Sharda. *Musings on Indian Writing in English*. New Delhi: Sarup & Sons. 2007.
- Mahapatra, Subhasini. *Reflections on Crime against Women*. New Delhi: Rajat Publications, 2006.
- Meera. K.R. *Hangwoman: Everyone Loves A Good Hanging*. Trans. From the Malayalam by J. Devika. New Delhi: Penguin Books, 2014.
- Naik, M.K. *A History of Indian English Literature*. New Delhi: Sahitya Akademi, 1995. · Rich, Adrienne. *Of Woman Born*. New York: W.W.Norton, 1976.
- Romito, Patrizia. *A Deafening silence: Hidden Violence against Women and Children*. Trans, by Janet Eastwood. UK: Polity Press, 2008. Print.
- Roy, Kalpna. *Women's Oppression and Protective Law*. Rajat Publications, 1999.
- Showalter, Elaine. *A literature of their own: British women novelists from Brontë to Lessing*. N.J.Princeton: Princeton University, 1977.
- Patricia Tjaden and Nancy Thoennes, "Effects of Interviewer Gender on Men's Responses to a Telephone Survey on Violent Victimization," *National Violence Against Women Survey*. 2000.
- Singh, Indu Prakash. *Indian Women: The Captured Beings*. New Delhi: Intellectual Publishing House, 1990.
- Wesely, Jennifer K. *Being Female: The Continuum of Sexualization*. United States of America: Lynne Rienner Publishers, 2012.
- Woolf, Virginia. *A Room of One's Own*. London: Hogarth Press, 1929.